

BIFURCATION AND LYAPUNOV EXPONENT OF A CHAOTIC CUBIC MAP

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Abstract

In recent years, increasing research activity in the field of nonlinear systems has shown that even simple dynamical models can produce complex, seemingly random-looking behaviour, including the appearance of chaos. The universality discovered by M.J. Feigenbaum [1], [2] with non-linear models has successfully led to observe that large classes of non-linear systems exhibit transitions to chaos through period doubling route. In this paper, we have considered a one parameter cubic map, obtained the fixed points / periodic points and bifurcation values of periods 2^n , $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ using suitable numerical methods and have shown how the ratio of three successive period doubling bifurcation points ultimately converge to the Feigenbaum constant. We have calculated the Feigenbaum α value [4] also. We have further verified our findings with the help of Time series analysis, Lyapunov exponent [6], [9] and the Bifurcation diagram of the cubic map.

Keywords: Period Doubling bifurcation / Chaos / Feigenbaum constant / Feigenbaum α value .
Lyapunov exponent

1. INTRODUCTION

Generally the nonlinear dynamics of physical systems are analyzed by obtaining discrete models, mathematically represented by maps. Maps arise in various ways : as tools for analyzing differential equations (eg. Poincare map), as models of natural phenomenon (as in economic or financial models etc.) or as simple examples of chaos. Maps are capable of much varied behaviour than differential equations because the points jump discontinuously along their orbits rather than flow continuously. Some useful concepts are highlighted below.

Definition

Let $f: R \rightarrow R$. The point x_0 is a fixed point for f if $f(x_0) = x_0$. The point x_c is a periodic point of period n for f if $f^n(x_0) = x_0$ but $f^i(x_0) \neq x_0$ for $0 < i < n$. A periodic point x_0 of period n is attracting if $\left| (f^n)'(x_0) \right| < 1$ and repelling if $\left| (f^n)'(x_0) \right| > 1$.

Definition

A bifurcation is a qualitative change in dynamics upon a small variation in the parameters of a system. Normally a gradual variation of a parameter in the system corresponds to the gradual variation of the solutions of the problem. However, there exists a large number of problems for which the number of solutions changes abruptly and the structure of solution set varies dramatically when a parameter passes through some critical values. This kind of phenomenon is called bifurcation and these parameter values are called bifurcation values (or bifurcation points).

Period- Doubling (P-D) bifurcations, as a universal route to chaos, is one of the most exciting discoveries in the field of nonlinear dynamical systems. There has been much interest in the chaotic behavior of simple dynamical systems in a variety of fields. Since, in many cases, chaotic behavior appears after the period-doubling phenomenon when a parameter is varied, it has been one of the important problems to analyze and describe the phenomenon theoretically. The period-doubling phenomenon implies a sequence of bifurcations in which a periodic orbit loses its stability and is replaced by a new stable one with the double period. These bifurcations accumulate at a certain point, where chaotic behavior begins to appear.

Feigenbaum has shown theoretically that there exist some universal properties in the period-doubling phenomenon [1], [2] of one dimensional mappings of the form $x_{n+1} = f(x_n, \lambda)$, where λ is a controllable parameter.

2. METHODS AND DISCUSSIONS

The nonlinear map of our interest is the cubic map $f(x) = (b-1)x - x^3$, where b is a parameter. Our first objective is to establish the Feigenbaum Universality in case of the this map.

Now, $f(x) = (b-1)x - x^3$, b is a parameter.

$$\Rightarrow f'(x) = b-1-3x^2$$

Hence $f'(x) = 0 \Rightarrow b-1-3x^2 = 0$. Solving this we get $x = \sqrt{\frac{b-1}{3}}$. Also

$f''(x) = -6x$. Hence for $x = \sqrt{\frac{b-1}{3}}$, $f''(x) = -6\sqrt{\frac{b-1}{3}} < 0$ for $b > 1$. Thus we get that

$x = \sqrt{\frac{b-1}{3}}$ for $b > 1$ is a point of maximum and the maximum value of the function is

given by $\frac{2(b-1)^{\frac{3}{2}}}{3^{\frac{3}{2}}}$. If we fix $b = 4$, then the maximum value of the function will be 2.

One of the main aims of bifurcation theory is to find fixed points, periodic points of maps and look for the region of their stability. The fixed points of the map are the solutions of the equation $f(x) = x$. These solutions are found to be $x = 0$, $\sqrt{b-2}$ and $-\sqrt{b-2}$. This shows that the fixed points other than $x = 0$ are not real for $b < 2$. Geometrically, the fixed points are nothing but points of intersection of the map and the line $y = x$. The following diagrams show that there are no fixed points other than $x = 0$ for our map if $b < 2$. In fact, all the trajectories for $b < 2$ settle at the fixed point $x = 0$ making the dynamics a trivial one. So, we restrict the parameter b between 2 and 4 and $x \in [0, 2]$.

Figure 1: Graphs showing the fixed points of f for $b = 2.0$ and $b = 3.0$

To discuss the stability of the above fixed points, we utilize the stability criterion which says that if $|f'(x)|_{x=x^*} < 1$ then the fixed point $x = x^*$ is stable, otherwise unstable.

Now, $f'(x)|_{x=0} = b - 1$ which will be greater than one in absolute value because $b > 2$. Hence $x = 0$ always remains as an unstable fixed point. Moreover, as we restrict $x \in [0, 2]$ we consider the fixed point $\sqrt{b-2}$ only and not the others. We see that for this fixed point $|f'(x)|_{x=\sqrt{b-2}} = |5 - 2b|$. Hence this fixed point will be stable in the region $2 < b < 3$. As b crosses the value 3, the stable fixed point $x = \sqrt{b-2}$ becomes an unstable one. Thus, a qualitative change in the behavior of the fixed point occurs at $b = 3$ of the parameter value. So we consider $b = b_1$ (say) $= 3$ as the first bifurcation point.

Since our main aim is to study the long term behavior of the map, so, after understanding the fate of the fixed points of f , we now consider the periodic points of period 2 and higher and look into their stability property. The period 2 points of the map are nothing but the fixed points of the second order iteration of the map. So, let us consider the iterated map $f^2(x)$. If we draw the graph of $f^2(x)$ with the line $y = x$, they will show more points of intersection, some of which are already found fixed points of f and the remaining are

periodic points of period 2. It is quite obvious that the fixed points of f are also fixed points of f^2 as $f(x) = x \Rightarrow f(f(x)) = f(x) \Rightarrow f^2(x) = x$.

Figure 2: Intersection of the graphs $f^2(x)$ and $y = x$ for $b = 3.0$ and $b = 3.5$

The period 2 points of the map are given by the solution of the equation $f^2(x) = x$. We find

$$f^2(x) = f(f(x)) = x^9 - 3bx^7 + 3x^7 + 3b^2x^5 - 6bx^5 + 3x^5 - b^3x^3 + 3b^2x^3 - 4bx^3 + 2x^3 + b^2x - 2bx + x$$

Hence $f^2(x) = x$ gives us the equation

$$x^9 - 3bx^7 + 3x^7 + 3b^2x^5 - 6bx^5 + 3x^5 - b^3x^3 + 3b^2x^3 - 4bx^3 + 2x^3 + b^2x - 2bx + x = x$$

The nine roots of the above equation are found to be

$$x = 0, \quad x = \sqrt{b-2}, \quad x = -\sqrt{b-2}, \quad x = \sqrt{b}, \quad x = -\sqrt{b}, \quad x = -\sqrt{-\frac{1}{2} + \frac{b}{2} - \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{b^2 - 2b - 3}}$$

$$x = -\sqrt{-\frac{1}{2} + \frac{b}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{b^2 - 2b - 3}}, \quad x = \sqrt{-\frac{1}{2} + \frac{b}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{b^2 - 2b - 3}}$$

$$\text{and } x = \sqrt{-\frac{1}{2} + \frac{b}{2} - \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{b^2 - 2b - 3}}$$

Out of these nine points, last two points are the only relevant periodic points of period 2 in our discussion as $x \in [0, 2]$, and valid only when $b \geq 3$ because they exist for $b \geq 3$. We reject the point $x = \sqrt{b}$ because it is always found to be unstable one.

Also note that, just below $b = 3$ trajectories converge to a single value of x and just above $b = 3$ the trajectories converges between two values of x . This means that the trajectories of the map undergo period doubling bifurcation for $b > 3$.

Let us see how the derivatives of the second iterate function change at the bifurcation value.

Now,

$$\frac{df^2(x)}{dx} = \frac{df(f(x))}{dx} = \frac{df}{dx} \Big|_{f(x)} \frac{df}{dx} \Big|_x$$

$$\text{Thus, } \frac{df^2(x)}{dx} \Big|_{x_{11}} = \frac{df}{dx} \Big|_{f(x_{11})} \frac{df}{dx} \Big|_{x_{11}}$$

$$= \frac{df}{dx} \Big|_{x_{12}} \frac{df}{dx} \Big|_{x_{11}} = \frac{df^2(x)}{dx} \Big|_{x_{12}}$$

Here, x_{11}, x_{12} are considered as periodic points of period two and hence we have

$$f(x_{11}) = x_{12} \text{ and } f(x_{12}) = x_{11}.$$

From above, we can conclude that both of these periodic points are either stable or both are unstable, and they have the same degree of stability or instability.

Now,

$$f^2(x) = x^9 - 3bx^7 + 3x^7 + 3b^2x^5 - 6bx^5 + 3x^5 - b^3x^3 + 3b^2x^3 - 4bx^3 + 2x^3 + b^2x - 2bx + x$$

$$\text{and } (f^2)'(x) = 9x^8 - 21bx^6 + 21x^6 + 15b^2x^4 - 30bx^4 + 15x^4 - 3b^3x^2 + 9b^2x^2 - 12bx^2 + 6x^2 + b^2 - 2b + 1$$

$$= -(-1 + b - 3x^2)(1 - b + 3x^2 - 6bx^2 + 3b^2x^2 + 6x^4 - 6bx^4 + 3x^6)$$

For $b = 3$, we have $(f^2)'(x) \Big|_{x=x_{11}} = 1$. Thus, for $b = 3$, the derivative of f^2 is equal to +1.

As b increases further the derivative of f^2 decreases and the fixed points become stable.

For e.g. if we calculate them for $b = 3.1$ they are found to be 0.18. These two fixed points of f^2 continue to be stable fixed points until $b = 3.2360679\dots$ [computed by computer program]. At this value of b , the derivative of f^2 evaluated at the above fixed point is equal to -1 and the value of b greater than 3.2360679\dots, the derivative is more negative than -1 so that numerically it becomes greater than 1. Hence, for b greater than $b = 3.2360679\dots$ the two fixed points becomes unstable. Thus a qualitative change in the behavior of the fixed point at $b = 3.2360679\dots$. So, $b = 3.2360679\dots$ is the second bifurcation point.

We find that for b just greater than 3.2360679\dots, the trajectories settle into a 4 cycle, i.e. the trajectory cycles among 4 values which we can label as x_1^* , x_2^* , x_3^* and x_4^* . To determine these periodic points we need to solve an equation whose degree is 81 ! viz $f^4(x) = x$, which can not be solved without the help of computer. So we use Computer programs to obtain fixed points, bifurcation values and the Feigenbaum δ and Feigenbaum α values.

3. MAIN RESULTS

We use Newton-Recurrence method and the Secant method mentioned in [8] to find the following fixed points/periodic points, bifurcation values and the corresponding values of Feigenbaum δ . Newton's formula is sensitive to the initial conditions and for the Secant formula we need two initial approximations. So, we find the first two bifurcation points analytically. Our calculated values are listed below.

Periods	Bifurcation values	δ values	α values
1	$b_1 = 3.0$		
2	$b_2 = 3.23606797750\dots$		
4	$b_3 = 3.28803175448\dots$	$\delta_1 = 4.542933390\dots$	$\alpha_1 = 2.68928\dots$
8	$b_4 = 3.29922793972\dots$	$\delta_2 = 4.641203752\dots$	$\alpha_2 = 2.71161\dots$
16	$b_5 = 3.30162891403\dots$	$\delta_3 = 4.663184109\dots$	$\alpha_3 = 2.71657\dots$

Periods	Bifurcation values	δ values	α values
32	$b_6 = 3.30214327158\dots$	$\delta_4 = 4.667909191\dots$	$\alpha_4 = 2.71764\dots$
64	$b_7 = 3.30225343774\dots$	$\delta_5 = 4.668925024\dots$	$\alpha_5 = 2.71786\dots$
128	$b_8 = 3.30227703225\dots$	$\delta_6 = 4.669142335\dots$	$\alpha_6 = 2.71791\dots$
256	$b_9 = 3.30228208549\dots$	$\delta_7 = 4.669188920\dots$	$\alpha_7 = 2.71792\dots$
512	$b_{10} = 3.3022831677\dots$	$\delta_8 = 4.669198886\dots$	$\alpha_8 = 2.71793\dots$
1024	$b_{11} = 3.3022833995\dots$	$\delta_8 = 4.669200795\dots$	$\alpha_9 = 2.71793\dots$
2048	$b_{12} = 3.3022834491\dots$	$\delta_8 = 4.669201980\dots$	$\alpha_{10} = 2.71793\dots$

The Feigenbaum constant is evaluated as $\delta = 4.669201980\dots$ which agrees with the actual Feigenbaum constant up to 6 decimal places. The nature of δ is universal i.e. it is same for a wide range of different iterators.

Also, the Feigenbaum α is found to be 2.71793 in our case. The Feigenbaum theory leading to the number $\alpha = 2.5029\dots$ applies only in the limit of high-order bifurcations while experiments are constrained to look at relatively low-order bifurcations. However, in those few cases in which α has been determined experimentally, reasonable but not exact agreement is found between the measured values and the predicted value of α given by the

$$\text{equation } \alpha = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{d_n}{d_{n+1}} = 2.5029 \text{ [4].}$$

And this constant is known as Feigenbaum constant and the importance of this constant is that once the bifurcation value attains this constant, the next region is dominated by chaos, where prediction about the system becomes impossible. Of course within the chaotic regions also there are few values of the parameter where regular behaviour occurs and this can be seen in the bifurcation diagram where periodic windows marked by white spaces is seen and where the Lyapunov exponent becomes negative.

4. TIME SERIES ANALYSIS

A type of plot that is frequently used for visualization of the solution of one dimensional difference equation of the form $x_{n+1} = f(x_n)$, $n=0, 1, \dots$ given by a map is called the time series. It consists of a representation of the variable x_n as a function of n . Typically the horizontal axis represents n and the vertical axis represents x_n . In case of the map we have considered, the difference equation is given by $x_{n+1} = (b - 1)x_n - x_n^3$, $n=0, 1, \dots$

For $b = 2.5$ (showing period one behaviour)

For $b = 3.1$ (showing period two behaviour)

For $b = 3.24$ (showing period four behaviour)

For $b = 3.33$ (showing chaotic behaviour)

Figure 3: Time series plot of the map for different values of the parameter.

The set towards which the x values converge is called an attractor. The above figures show that an attractor may be a fixed point, a limit cycle (or a periodic attractor) or a chaotic attractor. In case of the map, we have considered, if we start with a value of b greater than 2 but less than 3, successive points 'flow' to a fixed point at a non-zero value of x . However,

for values of b slightly greater than 3 the fixed point 'bifurcates' to a 'limit cycle' of period 2. This then bifurcates again i.e. the period doubles at a larger value of b to a limit cycle with period 4. As b increases, the period continues to double at successively closer and closer value of b until we have chaotic behaviour. In case of the map we have considered, this is illustrated in the above figures with four values of b ($b = 2.5$, fixed point), ($b = 3.1$, period 2 limit cycle), ($b = 3.24$, period 4 limit cycle) and ($b = 3.33$, chaos).

5. LYAPUNOV EXPONENT

A defining feature of a chaotic system is sensitivity to initial conditions. If two trajectories which start off close to each other deviate more and more with increasing time, the system is said to be chaotic. The rate at which nearby trajectories deviate from each other with time is characterized by a quantity called the Lyapunov exponent. Let us consider two iterations of our map starting from two values of x which are close together. Let the two starting values be x_0 and $x_0 + \delta x_0$ where δ is very small. These map to x_1 and $x_1 + \delta x_1, \dots, x_n + \delta x_n$. Expanding $f(x)$ about x_n we have $\delta x_n = f'(x_{n-1}) \delta x_{n-1}$ assuming that δx_n is sufficiently small. Hence the separation of the two trajectories after n steps, δx_n , is related to their

initial separation, δx_0 , by $\left| \frac{\delta x_n}{\delta x_0} \right| = \prod_{i=0}^{n-1} |f'(x_i)|$. We expect that this will vary

exponentially at large n like $\left| \frac{\delta x_n}{\delta x_0} \right| = e^{\lambda n}$ and so we define the Lyapunov exponent λ by

$\lambda = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \ln |f'(x_i)|$. Clearly, if $\lambda > 0$, neighbouring trajectories diverge from each

other at large n , which corresponds to chaos. However, if trajectories converge to a fixed point or a limit cycle they will get closer together, which corresponds to $\lambda < 0$. Hence, we can determine whether or not the system is chaotic by the sign of the Lyapunov exponent. Below, we have given the calculated values of the Lyapunov exponent for some values of the parameter b in case of our map. We have considered iteration size of 50000 for getting the values.

Parameter (b) Value	Lyapunov exponent	Parameter(b) Value	Lyapunov exponent
2.9	0.22310	3.5	0.49152
3.0	-0.00023	3.6	0.67972
3.1	-0.85734	3.7	-0.43438
3.2	-0.19280	3.8	0.80575
3.3	-0.05882	3.9	0.87913
3.4	0.34300	4.0	1.09861

Below we have shown the graph of lyapunov exponent versus the parameter value between 2 to 4. The graph also shows that almost after the value 3.30 of b the remaining lyapunov exponents become positive, showing the beginning of chaotic region. The figure further supports the first two bifurcation points as 3.0 and 3.23 where the lyapunov exponent is almost zero. Interestingly, after attaining the chaotic region at $b = 3.30$ (approx), we observe some scattered dots in the negative side of the x -axis. They signify that within the chaotic region also, at certain values of the parameter, there are regular behaviours. This is supported by the bifurcation diagram also which we have drawn in the next section.

Figure 4 Graph of calculated Lyapunov exponents versus the parameter b for $2 \leq b \leq 4$

6. BIFURCATION DIAGRAM AND CONCLUSION

A bifurcation diagram shows the possible values a function can have as function of the parameter of that function. It is a visual summary of the succession of period doubling produced as the parameter increases. In this diagram, the parameter is shown in the horizontal axis of the plot and the vertical axis shows the possible values of the function. The bifurcation diagram nicely shows the forking of the periods of stable orbits from 1 to 2, then 2 to 4 etc. The interesting thing about the diagram is that as the periods go to infinity, still the parameter remains finite.

Figure 5. Bifurcation diagram for the parameter b for $1 < b \leq 4$

In case of our considered map, we see that for b less than 2, all the points are plotted at zero. This implies that zero is the one point attractor for b less than 2. For b between 2 and 3, we still have one point attractors but the 'attracted' value of x increases as b increases, at least to $b = 3$. Bifurcation occurs at $b = 3, 3.23606797750\dots, 3.28803175448\dots, \dots$ (approximately). The bifurcation diagram supports our numerically calculated bifurcation points. Just beyond $b = 3.3022834491\dots$ the system becomes chaotic. However, the system is not chaotic for all values of b greater than $3.3022834491\dots$. If we zoom into the figure, we see that at several values of b , greater than this value, a small number of x values are

visited. These regions produce the 'white space' which are also termed as the 'periodic window' in the diagram. Below, we have shown the bifurcation diagram between the parameter values 3.0 and 4. There is a rich interleaving of chaos and order. A small change in b can make a stable system chaotic, and vice versa.

Figure 6 : Bifurcation diagram for the parameter b for $3 \leq b \leq 4$

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